

PERINATAL MENTAL HEALTH:

**MENINALAB CITIZEN SCIENCE PROCESS TO
ESTABLISH RECOMMENDATIONS FOR
IMPROVING HEALTHCARE SERVICES RELATED
TO MENTAL HEALTH AND WELLBEING
DURING PREGNANCY**

MENINA4Sustain Policy Brief 2026

Entities coordinating the MENINA4Sustain project:

Funded entity:

1. Executive Summary

Perinatal mental health is a key determinant of maternal, infant and family wellbeing. Despite progress in the Valencian Community, care remains fragmented. This policy brief has been elaborated as a result of the MENINA4Sustain project; a citizen science initiative to improve mental health and wellbeing during pregnancy by organizing a citizen innovation lab (MENINALab) to generate new solutions that improve perinatal mental health. This MENINALab has actively involved pregnant women, moms and healthcare professionals in a co-creation process.

Barriers and challenges have been identified as well as strategic solutions and recommendations to face perinatal mental health are presented below for policy decision making.

2. Background and Rationale

The perinatal period is a time of vulnerability. Mental health problems are common and often untreated, affecting maternal wellbeing and infant development.

3. Key Barriers Identified

Individual level	Support level	Professional level	Organizational level	Social and policy level
<ul style="list-style-type: none">•Stigma•Low literacy•Fear of judgement•Information sources•Lack of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none">•Unequal support•Lack of support network	<ul style="list-style-type: none">•Lack of training in mental health issues•Not enough information and communication pregnancy aspects•Lack of systematic mental health screenings	<ul style="list-style-type: none">•Fragmented teams (hospital + Primary care + mental health)•Lack of professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none">•Inequalities•Insufficient structural support

4. MENINALab citizen science process

A citizen innovation lab (MENINALab) took place on the Elda Healthcare Department facilities (Petrer, Valencian Community) on the last trimester of 2025. It has been coordinated by Fisabio Foundation and the Healthcare Department. It involved 25 pregnant women, moms and healthcare professionals from pregnancy follow-up.

During 3 co-creation sessions MENINALab generated 9 solutions to overcome 3 challenges related to perinatal mental health:

Lack of training and promotion of mental health

Lack of emotional support to pregnant women

Lack of information and communication during pregnancy process

5. Solutions and recommendations for Public Hospitals and Regional Health Authorities for the improvement of healthcare services in relation to perinatal mental health.

Governance and planning

- To create a regional perinatal mental health strategy including "mental health plan" and being co-created with citizens.
- To define accessible spaces (physical, cognitive) at hospitals and Primary Care Centers to improve information provided by the Public Health System (considering people with other languages, low educational, etc.)

Healthcare services

- To create multidisciplinary teams (obstetricians, midwives, sexologists, psychologists, etc.)
- Improve channels and tools for increasing the pregnancy process information and related consultations and doubts.
- Create a personalize chatbot for pregnant women feed with scientific evidence (recommendations, information regarding different phases of pregnancy, treatments, proceedings, etc.)
- Establishing routine screening and considering mental health clinical record of the patients.
- Promote internal care pathways

Workforce capacity

- More training and capability in mental health issues to healthcare professionals that are in pregnancy follow-up.
- To create new maternal educational courses with women and since the beginning of the pregnancy to cover all doubts and information at each pregnancy stage.

Support

- Promote active listening to the patient
- Considering inclusion issues (translation services, social work more involved, etc.)
- Create support networks formed by volunteers, pregnant women and healthcare professionals
- To design integral programmes from Primary Care Centers to promote wellbeing activities with women and childs.

This citizen science initiative has been possible thanks to the active participation of 25 women co-creating during the different MENINALab sessions process. We thank them for their involvement, dedication and illusion.